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DAZL activation is a transcriptional property of transformation.

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We describe DAZL modulation as a transformation-associated event and likely transcriptional property functioning in a broader imprinting system recurrently activated in human cancer. PRDM1 activation resulting from PRDM14 expression results in DAZL induction, and a PRDM1-DAZL interaction was identified. PRDM1 has transformation potential that rivals (but does not reach) bona fide oncogene and tumor suppressor deficiency; the mechanism by which PRDM1 exerts oncogenic potential may be related to a contribution of the Xist-associated imprinting system to transformation in humans.

Citations

1. Li, H., Liang, Z., Yang, J., Wang, D., Wang, H., Zhu, M., Geng, B. and Xu, E.Y., 2019. DAZL is a master translational regulator of murine spermatogenesis. National science review, 6(3), pp.455-468.